

N. A. Belletty, Esq., Civil Assistant, Topographical Survey of India, proposed by Captain H. H. G. Austen, and seconded by Mr. Grote.

Dr. J. J. Wood, officiating Garrison Assistant Surgeon, Fort William, proposed by Dr. Ewart, and seconded by Dr. Partridge.

The Council reported that they have elected the following gentlemen to fill up vacancies in the several Committees.

In the Library Committee,—H. B. Medlicott, Esq., and Cumár Harendra Krishna Deva.

In the Natural History Committee,—H. B. Medlicott, Esq., V. Ball, Esq., Dr. J. Ewart, and, Mr. Justice Norman.

In the Statistical Committee,—Mr. Justice Phear.

In the Linguistic Section of the Ethnological Committee,—Mr. Justice Markby.

A letter was read from Lieutenant-Colonel H. Raban, intimating his desire to withdraw his name from the Society.

Letters were read—

7. From the Director of Public Instruction, forwarding a copy of Mr. Cowell's Report on the Toles of Nuddea.

No. 1547.

*From the Director of Public Instruction,
To the Secretary of the Asiatic Society.*

Dated Fort William, 9th April, 1867.

SIR,—I have the honor to forward herewith, for the information of the Asiatic Society, a copy of a report on the Sanskrit Toles of Nuddea by Mr. E. B. Cowell, late Principal of the Sanskrit College.

I have the honor to be,

Sir,

Your most obedient Servant,

W. S. ATKINSON,

Director of Public Instruction.

*From E. B. COWELL, Esq., late Principal, Sanskrit College, Calcutta,
to W. S. ATKINSON, Esq., Director of Public Instruction,—(dated
the 19th January, 1867.)*

SIR,—I have the honor to forward you my Nuddea Report. As I have added at the end some remarks on its necessary defects and the causes of my long delay in sending it, I need not repeat them here.

I may add that the report would have been finished before I left India, if my time had not been occupied by some communications about the Madrassah, which took off my thoughts from the report.

I hope the report will be of some use, as it is. I wish I could return for a month to Nuddea, to makè it better.

From E. B. COWELL, Esq., late Principal of the Sanskrit College, to W. S. ATKINSON, Esq., Director of Public Instruction,—dated the 17th January, 1867.

SIR,—I have the honor to forward to you the following report of my visit, in 1864, to the Toles of Nuddea :—

In accordance with your instructions I proceeded thither with Mr. Woodrow, and we were accompanied by Pandit Mahesa Chandra Nyáyaratna, one of the Professors of the Sanskrit College, with whom I have for some years studied Nyáya, and to whose wide attainments in Hindu philosophy, as well as general ability and learning, I can testify from personal knowledge in the highest degree. We left Calcutta on Monday the 29th of February, and made Krishnagur our head quarters, whence we made daily excursions to Nuddea, which is about ten miles distant. I must not omit to mention that we received much attention from the Mahárájá of Nuddea, who held a *quasi* durbar of Pandits, which enabled us to make the acquaintance of many who did not reside in Nuddea itself. I returned to Calcutta on the 8th of March.

The word Tole (টোল) is a Bengali word of uncertain derivation ; but there are at least two Sanskrit words for the thing itself, *chatúsh-páthi*, i. e., a place where the four vedas are studied, and *maṭha*. The former does not seem to be an ancient word, as I do not find any authority for it in the St. Petersburg Sanskrit Dictionary, except the Sabda Kalpa Drúma of Rájáh Rádhá Kánta Deva ; but *maṭha* is an old word and occurs at least as far back as the Amara Kosha.

The institution is curious and interesting, as being undoubtedly a remnant of old times. It represents, in fact, the same state of feeling in ancient India as that which we find in ancient Greece, and which so continually comes up in Plato's controversies with the Sophists or paid Professors of his day, viz., the popular prejudice against receiving mercenary reward for the communication of knowledge. The Pandit of a tole should properly not only instruct his pupils gratuitously,

but he should also provide them with food, clothing and lodging, during their stay under his teaching. He himself is to be remunerated indirectly by the invitations and presents which celebrity as a teacher would ensure his receiving at the religious ceremonies of the neighbouring zemindars. Thus my own visit was delayed some weeks in consequence of all the principal Pandits of Nuddea being absent, as they had gone to attend the *çraddha* of the late Rájáh of Cooch Behar. The tole system of Nuddea has, however, degenerated in this as in other respects. The Pandits of most toles in other districts still lodge and feed their pupils; but those of Nuddea, with very few exceptions, have been able to break through this custom. They now only supply their pupils with lodging, the reputation of Nuddea no doubt enabling them to attract students from other toles in spite of the greater inducements which the latter offer.

The chief studies of Nuddea are *Smṛiti* and *Nyáya*. It is the latter, especially, for which its name is celebrated all over India. Other provinces have their own peculiar schools of law, and Nuddea, therefore, can generally only attract students of Bengal to its *Smṛiti* toles; but in logic it has an unrivalled reputation. Chaitanya, the celebrated reviver of the mystic worship of *Krishna* at the close of the 15th century, was a native of this place; and it has produced a succession of great *Naiyáyika* teachers, whose names are household words in every *Pandit* family in India. In fact the name of Nuddea is associated with the latest development of the *Nyáya* philosophy.

The ancient *Sutras* or *Aphorisms* of Gotama do not represent the modern logic of India; and although the recent school may have added little or nothing to the real discoveries of the Hindu Aristotle, they have undoubtedly elaborated a most refined system of *logomachy*, far surpassing in subtilty and ingenuity all the scholastic disputations of mediæval Europe.

One of the most celebrated mediæval logicians was Gangeça *Upádhya*ya of Mithilá, who wrote a large treatise, called the *Chintámani*, in four sections on the four *Naiyáyika pramánas* or sources of knowledge, *i. e.*, perception, inference, comparison, and testimony. It is this work which has furnished the text to the modern Nuddea school. Its most renowned members are the following.

1. Raghunátha *Çiromani*, who wrote a commentary on the first two sections of the *Chintámani*. This is called the *Didhiti*.

2. Mathurá Nátha Tarkavágiça, who wrote a gloss on the *Didhiti* and also an original comment on *Gangeça*.

3. Jagadiça Tarkálankára, who also wrote a commentary on part of the *Didhiti* as well as many other works, especially a very celebrated treatise on logic and grammar, called the *çabda-çakti-prakáçiká*.

4. Gadádharma Bhattáchárya, who wrote a commentary on the *Didhiti* and a series of works, such as the *Vishayatá-vádártha*, &c., on the abstrusest mysteries of the modern logic.

5. Çankara Tarkavágiça, who wrote a commentary called *Patriká*, on the harder passages of Mathurá Nátha, Jagadiça, and Gadádharma. He seems to have flourished about sixty or seventy years ago: and it is he who is said to have brought to its height the present vicious system of disputatious logomachy which prevails in *Nuddea*.

A *tole* is generally a mere collection of mud hovels round a quadrangle, in which the students live in the most primitive manner possible. The *Paṇḍit* does not reside with them, but comes to teach them on the lawful days. Each student has his own hut, with his brass waterpot and mat, and few have any other furniture. Most make their own copies of the books they use, and a large part of the year is vacation, during which they wander over the surrounding country on begging expeditions; but during the reading months much hard mental labour is undoubtedly gone through. On one side of the quadrangle there is a "lecture hall," usually on a raised platform, some three feet from the ground; it is open on one side, and just sheltered on the other three from the rain and wind. In some *toles* it is only a thatched shed; in others it is a little more elaborate. Only one *tole* in *Nuddea* can boast of any external adornment. This is the *tole* of *Paṇḍit Prasanna Chandra Tarkaratna*. It was built for him by a *Bábú* of Lucknow, and is really an elegant building, occupying about a beegah and a half of land. The quadrangle inside is about thirty yards square and contains thirty rooms for the students. The rooms are generally about nine feet long and eight wide, with a window and door; the corner rooms are rather larger. More than half of one side is given up to a lecture hall or *dálán*. This stands on a platform raised some five feet from the ground; it has two apartments, each about thirty-three feet in length, the outer is ten, the inner twelve feet wide; and the front is supported by six pillars

which produce a very good effect. The other toles have no architectural display whatever. Everything is of a more than Spartan simplicity; and one cannot help honouring the zeal for knowledge, however misdirected the zeal or useless the knowledge, which leads so many students, generation after generation, to devote themselves to such monastic privations and hardships. The love of fame is, no doubt, the motive with many. The fact of having studied at Nabadwipa and gained an *upádhi* there, will ensure respect for a Pandit in every part of India, from Lahore to Travancore. But there are some who are led by less worldly motives. These come to study Nyáya, as students came to the University of Paris in the middle ages, and one can hardly fail to be reminded of Chaucer's lines about—

“The clerk of Oxenforde also
That unto logik hadde long ygo;
As lene was his horse as is a rake,
And he was not right fat, I undertake.
And able that he was a philosophre,
Yet hadde he but litel gold in cofre.”

I could not help looking at those unpretending lecture halls with a deep interest, as I thought of the Pandits lecturing there to generation after generation of eager inquisitive minds. Seated on the floor with his ‘corona’ of listening pupils round him, the teacher expatiates on those refinements of infinitesimal logic which make a European's brain dizzy to think of, but whose labyrinth a trained Nuddea student will thread with unfaltering precision. I noticed during my visit middle-aged and even grayhaired men among the students of the celebrated toles, and some of these had come from such widely different homes as Lahore, Pooree, and the Tamil country.

I visited every tole in Nuddea, and examined every one with my Pandit more or less thoroughly. The following is a list; but the number of the students is probably not wholly accurate, as of course no register of attendance is kept, and it was not easy to decide whether absent students were really to be counted on the rolls or not. Professor Wilson found from 500 to 600 pupils at the time of his visit in 1829, the number is now less than 150. Part of the decrease may no doubt be attributed to the prevalence of the epidemic which has driven many away, and prevented others from

coming; but there are other and permanent causes at work for the overthrow of the scholastic glory of Nuddea.

Smṛiti.

1. The tole of *Brajanáth Vidyáratna*. Here there were seventeen students, four from the districts round Nuddea (*deçiya*,) and thirteen from other parts of Bengal (*bideçi*.) Those from Bengal came from Dacca, Rungpore, Dinajpore, Jessore, Rajshahi, and Pubna.

2. That of *Rámnáth Tarkasiddhánta*. Here there were ten *bideçi* and five *deçiya* students. The former came from Jessore, Khunla near Dacca, Dacca, Tripur, and Burisal.

3. That of *Madhusudan Nyáyaratna*, the brother of Hara Mohan Chudámani. Here there were three *deçiya* and seven *bideçi* students, the latter from Jessore and Burisal.

4. That of *Haridása Çiromani*. Here there were four students, two from the neighbouring district and two from Dacca.

5. That of *Çib Náth Bidyábáchaspati*. Here there were four students, two of whom came from Midnapore and one from Jessore; the fourth was a native of the Nuddea District.

6. That of *Prasanna Cúmár Vidyáratna*, brother of the deceased Çri Rám Tarkaratna. Here there were fourteen students, twelve of whom were *bideçi*, *i. e.*, as coming from Burisal, Dacca, and Chittagong.*

Nyáya.

1. That of the two brothers, *Hara Mohan Chudámani* and *Bhuvanmohan Vidyáratna*, and their uncle, *Raghúmani Vidyábhushan*. Here there were twenty-one students, four *deçiya* and seventeen *bideçi*,—the latter from Furreedpore, Burisal, Dacca, Midnapore, Jessore, Mithilá, and one even from Nepal.

2. That of *Prasanna Chandra Tarkaratna*. Here there were eighteen students, fourteen of whom were *bideçi*, *i. e.*, six from Mithilá, five from Delhi and Lahore, two from Pooree and one from the Tamil country.

3. That of *Mádhava Chandra Tarkasiddhánta*. Here there were sixteen students, eight of whom were *bideçi*, *i. e.*, four from Bakla near Comilla, two from Dinajpore, and two from Jessore.

* His pupils were quite middle-aged and some greyheaded. They wished to read with him, though a young man of twenty-five, as he belonged to a family long renowned as Smarta Pandits.

4. That of *Hari Náth Tárkasiddhánta*. Here there were thirteen students, ten of whom were *bideçí*, i. e., five from Midnapore, four from Mithilá, and one from Nepal.

5. That of *Krishna Kánta Çíroratna*. Here there were two students, both from Jessore.

6. That of *Brahmaçrama Swámi*, a dandi Goswami.

He had lately had seven students, but only one was with him at the time of my visit. His former house was destroyed by an inundation of the river. Before him it had been occupied by a very celebrated *dandi* named Swayam Prakáça; and tradition reports that it was at that house that the once projected College of Nuddea was to have been established.

Thus at the time of my visit I found only twelve toles. Professor Wilson in 1829 appears to have found twenty-five!

Besides these regular toles, there is also an udásin or ascetic recluse from Pooree, named Káçi Náth Çástri, who teaches Vedánta to the students of other toles:—

The following are some of the celebrated pandits in Nuddea without toles.

1. Lál Mohan Vidyábhushan.
2. Nanda Kumár Vidyábhushan. These two are very learned in Smṛiti.

The following are profoundly versed in Nyáya:—

3. Umácharan Tarkaratna.
4. Rájnaráyana Nyáyabhushan.
5. Nilmani Sárvaabhauma.
6. Surya Kánta Vidyálankár.
7. Raghumañi Tarkapanchánan.
8. Umá Kánta Nyáyaratna.
9. Purushottam Nyáyaratna.

Of course there are also many toles in the villages round Nuddea, these I did not visit; but I particularly heard of that of Lakshmi Kánta Nyáyabhushan, the purohit or family priest of the Mahárájáh. He teaches Smṛiti at Barigachhi, about ten miles to the north of Nuddea. I also heard a good deal of the Nyáya tole of Prasanna Chandra Nyáyaratna at Belpokhar, three kroses north of Nuddea. This Pandit was one of the six who signed the petition to the

Lieutenant-Governor, the other five being, I believe, Nuddea Pandits. He told me that he had twenty-two students, eleven *deçiya* and eleven *bideçí* from Mithilá, Burdwan and Delhi.

The Smṛiti students are said generally to study at a tole for eight years, the Nyáya for ten years.* All toles are closed for ten days in each month, *i. e.*, on the 1st (*pratipada*), the 8th (*ashtami*), 13th (*trayodaçi*) 14th (*chaturdaçi*) and 15th (*purnamasi*) of each paksha or fortnight, beside two weeks for the Saraswatee pooja and occasionally for other parvas. In Nyáya toles they close from *Ratha* to *Rása*, *i. e.*, from *Áshádh*a to *Kártika* (five months). In Smṛiti toles they close for three months, from *Bhádra* to *Kártika*. But of course the studies are liable to irregular interruptions when the Pandits receive invitations from the zemindars. During the vacations the students go on begging expeditions (much as Hindoo and Buddhist ascetics have been famed for doing from immemorial times), or they return to their homes.

The studies at the Nuddea toles are chiefly confined to the following works, or parts of works, on logic and law:—

The chief works read in Nyáya or Logic are, besides the well known standard works, the *Bhášhá-parichchheda* and its commentary the *Siddhánta Muktváli*.

1. For *Vyápti* or the doctrine of the syllogism (comprising also the endless subtleties on *pakshatá*, or the conditions and rules relating to the minor term in its connection with the major term and the middle), the commentaries on the *Didhiti* by *Mathuránátha*, *Jagadiça* and *Gadádharma*.

2. For *hetwabhasa* or the fallacies, the commentaries of *Jagadiça* and *Gadádharma*.

3. For *Sámányalakshana jnána* (one of the most abstruse discussions of Hindu logic, referring to the transcendental perception, by which the mind, as it were, seizes the class in the individual, or, more properly, sees all the individuals under the one now present to the eye), the commentary of *Jagadiça*.

4. The *Kusumánjali*, or the celebrated attempt of *Udayana*

* Of course but for the continued interruptions the course of study could be finished in half the time.

Acharya to establish on Naiyáyik arguments the existence of the Supreme Being.*

5. The Çabda çakti prakáçiká of Jagadîça.

The chief works on Law or Smriti are—

1. Parts of Raghunandana's Ashtávinçati Tattwa.
2. Dáyabhága.
3. The Çráddha viveka.
4. The Práyacçhitta viveka.

The peculiarities of the Nuddea scholastic training may be summed up at once by a reference to that part of Bacon's *Novum Organon* which describes the system of scholastic logic still current in his day. In the 29th Aphorism of the first book he says that those sciences which are founded on opinions and arbitrary dogmas have a natural affinity to anticipation rather than to interpretation, and to the scholastic logic rather than to his proposed induction, for their object was to subdue assent, not things; to win victory in a disputation over an antagonist, not to extend man's dominion over nature. We have here an exact account of Nuddea logic, and the class of men whom it tends to educate,—its sole end is *vichára*, to win victory at a festival by clever arguments which silence the opponent for the time being. Many Pandits devote most of their attention to the *purvapakshas*, *i. e.*, those parts of the popular treatises which give at great length the arguments of the opposite side to the author,—it being the established rule in Hindu dialectics that every writer must present at full his opponents' views and exhaust all that can be adduced in their favour, before he proceeds to overthrow all that has been brought forward and to establish his own opinion.† These Pandits are thus enabled to stock themselves with a store of plausible arguments to oppose a popularly received opinion, and thus to win the credit of ably supporting an apparently hopeless cause. The very form of Hindu logic necessitates

* This has been edited with an English translation by the author of this Report.

† The writer has heard Pundit Iswar Chunder Vidyasagar relate how he first conceived his disgust at the native Nyáyá, when as a student he once spent a week of hard labour to master some abstruse opinion, which day after day was elucidated and at length made clear by the teacher. When the class met the next day, the first thing they heard was, "now this view is only the *purvapaksha*, we must now proceed to shew that it is incorrect."

error,—it is so fatally bound up with technical terms, that it inevitably degenerates into a mere playing with words; and this tendency, which is to some extent an inherent fault in European, as well as Hindu, mediæval logic, becomes exaggerated to its height in the modern Nuddea school.

In three of the toles we had the students exercise themselves in a discussion; and it was very curious to watch the intense eagerness of the disputants, as well as the earnest sympathy of the surrounding students and Pandits. A successful sophism elicited a smile of approbation from all.

The subject of one of these disputations was *Sādhyābhāva* or the absence of the major term. I could not follow the intricacies of the argument, but its summary was as follows.—

All accept that *Sādhyābhāva* means the absolute absence of fire, as, *e. g.*, in a lake of water. But how is this to be understood?

a.—In the sentence the lake has the total absence of fire or is totally destitute of fire; it cannot be merely meant that *all* fire collectively is absent, because this equally applies to a volcano, as that has indeed fire, but it is only mountainous fire and not kitchen fire. The sentence would, in fact, be useless, as it would be as true of any thing in the world as of your lake,—nothing can have *all* fire in it. *b.*—Again, as the volcano has the absence of fire and a jar, *i. e.*, has not fire and a jar both together, this is another way in which we might say that the same description would apply (if unlimited) to a volcano and a lake. *c.*—If you say the lake has *Kebala-vahni-abhāva*, *i. e.*, has the absence of fire alone, this gives rise to a quibble on the meaning of ‘alone.’ This is met by defining it, as “it is not the absence of anything besides fire but only the absence of fire,” (বহীতরের অভাব নহে কিন্তু বহির অভাব), this stops the apparent fault (or fallacy) of *Ubhayapaksha*. Then comes the question, “what is the meaning of the absence of all fire?” It is explained by কোন বহি না থাক, there not being any fire there,—now in the mountain there is *some* (কোন) fire, and it is the absence of *any* (কোন) that distinguishes the lake. Then comes the question, what is meant by ‘anything besides fire?’ Does fire mean here mountain-fire or any kind of fire, and so on, for ever? For the series of endlessly emerging quibbles is never stopped by the exhaustion of the subject, but only of the disputants or the audience.

At the present time all *vichāras* are of this kind,—not to elucidate the real meaning (for this is accepted on the authority of the writer), but to endeavour to establish or overthrow some verbal quibble which seeks to impugn the perfect accuracy of the definition.

In the teaching of the Pandits everything is directed to one end, *ad bene disputandum*. The primeval fault of the Hindu intellect has always been an excessive tendency to note the differences of things;* and of course such teaching in logic and law only fosters this defect to the highest possible degree.

As a specimen, I would subjoin a disquisition on the nature of prohibition given by Pandit Brajanāth Vidyāratna, the leading teacher of Smṛiti.

A student was selected during my visit to his tole to read and explain a portion of one of Raghunandana's *Tattwas*. The passage brought up the question of prohibition or *Nishedha*, and this led to the Pandit's giving a lecture on its nature and object.

I must here premise that in Hindu logic there are three kinds of *abhāva*, i. e., non-existence or absence.† These are respectively called "antecedent" (*prāgabhāva*), "emergent" (*dhwansābhāva*) and "absolute" (*atyantābhāva*). The first is the non-existence of a jar before it is made, which lasts from eternity down to the moment of its production and then ceases. The second is the non-existence of a jar when it is broken, which begins from the moment of its fracture and goes on to eternity forward. The third or absolute non-existence is seen in such sentences, as "there is no jar on this spot;" even if you move the jar thereto, there will be no jar in its former spot. The non-existence is always seen necessarily *somewhere*, else the jar would be omnipresent.

Now the Pandit maintained that the object of "command" (or *vidhi*) was to produce action or activity (*pravṛitti*); and similarly the object

* This tendency was at once the strength and weakness of the self-developed Hindu mind. Compare *Novum Organon*, i. iv. "Maximum et velut radicale discrimen ingeniorum, quoad philosophiam et scientias, illud est; quod alia ingenia sunt potiora et aptiora ad notandas rerum differentias, alia ad notandas rerum similitudines. Utrumque ingenium facile labitur in excessum, prensando aut gradus rerum aut umbras."

† Properly there are four, but the fourth (mutual or inter-exclusive non-existence) does not come in here. This is in fact our 'difference;' thus a jar and a chair mutually exclude one another, i, e., they are different things.

of *nishedha* or "prohibition" was to produce the absence (or non-existence) of activity, *i. e.* *pravritter abháva*. Now the question arises to which of the three kinds of *abháva* does this belong?

He first shewed that it could not be the third or "absolute" *abháva*, as this would imply that the absence *must* always exist somewhere, whether the prohibition be given or not. Neither could it be the "emergent," as this would imply that the actions prohibited must necessarily have been previously done, before the prohibition could exist,—as if there could be no such thing as prevention but only cure! He therefore, concluded by exhaustion that the non-existence of action which a prohibition produced in its hearers was "antecedent" or *prágabháva*. In other words, until the prohibition is promulgated, the actions which it is to prohibit are of course not prohibited; they are not, therefore, *so long* the objects of its injunction; they only become so from the moment of its being issued. From the moment of its issue, these actions are forbidden, *i. e.*, the hearer of the law will thenceforth not do them. There will therefore, in his case, be an absence of such prohibited actions, which will continue until he violates the law; and this absence will of course reach back to eternity, as until the prohibition came, he never could have committed them as prohibited. In other words, the non-existence of prohibited actions ceases only when, *after the prohibition*, some such action is performed.*

This I think, is a fair and perhaps favourable specimen of the niceties of what Dr. Hall has well called "the arcana of Hindu dialectics."†

One of the things which most interested and surprised me in my visit to Nuddea was the great desire which I found everywhere existing for English education. Of course amongst the *bideçi* students this did not exist; the grown up and elderly men who come to Nuddea to complete a purely Pandit education, only care for studies which will gain them reputation at home; but it is very different with the *deçiya* students. I was continually receiving applications from the students for a free

* The Pundit's reasoning is perhaps illustrated by Gibbon's remark on the injustice of a retro-active enactment, "which punishes offences which *did not exist at the time they were committed.*" (*Autobiography*, p. 80.)

† A contribution towards an index to the Bibliography of the Indian Philosophical systems, p. 32.

education in the Sanskrit College; everywhere the desire was expressed for a good Anglo-Sanskrit School. Such a school would effect more than anything else to abolish prejudice and to let light into a district which has long been a home of superstition and bigotry. The Church Missionary Society have long had a grant-in-aid school there. During the time of the Reverend S. Hasel, Sanskrit used to be taught there to a certain extent; but what is wanted is a thoroughly good school, educating up to the Entrance Examination, and at the same time giving a sound training in Sanskrit Grammar and Poetry. Perhaps the existing school could be adapted to this purpose, if the Church Missionary Society were disposed heartily to enter into it. Anyway the establishment of such a school, either by the Church Missionary Society or by Government, appears to me to be a pressing want, and I should indeed rejoice if my visit resulted in such a measure. Compared to this, the question of improving the toles is a measure of very secondary importance.

This leads me to notice a very interesting feature in Nuddea, which I was much surprised to find, and which seems to me a very remarkable proof, how a public demand is beginning to make itself felt for a better education than that given by the toles, even among the orthodox Hindu population. I refer to the *Akhaḍás* (আখড়া). These are schools kept by pupils of the Smṛiti or Nyáya toles, who here become in their turn teachers of grammar. I visited two of these schools, one held in the house of Pandit Rám Náth Tarkasiddhánta, and taught by Çri Náráyan Bhattáchárjya and Çri Mádhab Bhattáchárjya. Here there were twelve students. The second was held in the house of Pandit Rádhaballabha Bhattácháryya and was taught by Kumuda Nátha Çiromani and several other tole students. Here there were twenty-five scholars. In this *Akhaḍá* three students had finished the native grammar *Mugdhobodha*, and began to read Kálidása's poem, the *Kumára Sâmbhava*. I was interested to learn that two of the lads studying there were descendants in the seventh generation from the celebrated Pandit Jagadiça. In the first 'Akhaḍa' a little English was also taught, and the first book of reading was in use. This last fact seems to me most significant, that even in Nuddea, the centre of Hindoo exclusiveness, in a school entirely under the management of tole

students, a provision was made, however imperfect, for teaching some little smattering of the language and learning of the West.

The toles of Nuddea receive at present an annual pension from Government of Rupees 1,200. The history of this grant appears to be as follows:—

The Committee of Revenue found in 1784 that the Rájáh of Nuddea used to grant an allowance to the Padooás (পড়ুয়া) or Sanskrit students of the toles, and in September 1784 they appear, to a certain extent, to have sanctioned an annual grant of Rupees 1,200 to this object. It was paid from the Treasury of Nuddea, and distributed to the students by a person on the part of the zemindars.*

On the 18th May, 1787 (further enquiry having been instituted) the Board of Revenue directed the Collector to continue the payment of the pension for the present, and to charge the same under the head of 'Pension.' On the strength of this order it was regularly paid to the students at the rate of Rupees 100 per mensem. In 1829, at the request of the Collector of Nuddea, the Civil Auditor (April 6th) made a reference enquiring as to the authority on which the pension was granted. The Board on the 6th June quoted their letter of the 18th May, 1787, and at the same time stated thus—"There is no mention whatever of this allowance on the accounts or correspondence relating to the decennial settlement; and if the payment has been continued without enquiring on the authority, it ought to be immediately suspended and a full explanation of the irregularity furnished by the Collector." The allowance was in consequence discontinued, but a remonstrance from the Nuddea students was received with the recommendations of the Moorshedábád Commissioners, dated 22nd January, 1830, and was submitted to Government on the 12th February.

Meanwhile the late Professor H. H. Wilson (then Junior Member and Secretary to the General Committee of Public Instruction) had visited the toles and reported on their state; and in a letter dated 3rd August, 1830, Government sanctioned the

* Professor Wilson in his Report describes this distribution as it existed in his time, 1829. It was given to the bidesi students, *i. e.*, those who came from places more than three days' journey from Nuddea, and it allowed them from twelve annas to one rupee per mensem.

continuance of the pension with arrears, and the payment has continued to the present time.

Professor Wilson remarks in his Report—"Although the value of the learning acquired at Nuddea may not be very highly estimated by Europeans, yet it is in great repute with the natives, and its encouragement even by the trifling sum awarded is a gracious and popular measure :” of course, with the spread of English education in Lower Bengal the native estimate of the value of “infinitesimal logic” and the toles which teach it, is gradually altering, and I have heard many of the most able English scholars among the natives speak somewhat strongly against the system. As it is at present conducted, there can be no doubt that the Nyáya toles of Nuddea teach very little that is of any worth, either for practical life or even the history of the human mind; but this partly arises, not from the barren nature of Hindu logic, but the barrenness of the special part of it, to which they exclusively confine their attention. It is, as if in Oxford we neglected the Organon of Aristotle, and exclusively studied “the Farrago of the Parva Logicalia.”* But if the really great writers on Hindu logic were systematically taught in the toles of Nuddea, I should hardly be inclined to condemn as worthless all that the students would learn there. As it is, they learn only a part even of Nyáya, and I found that very few could read any portion of the Kusumánjali, or knew much beyond the endless intricacies of *Vyápti* and *pakshatá*. Here of course they were completely at home,—it was a marvel to see how completely.

I am hardly prepared to suggest a definite plan for the improvement of the Nuddea toles, because I think that this would require a practical acquaintance with Mofussil education, which I do not possess. But there are two suggestions which I would venture to make :—

1. It would be a great improvement, if some superintendence could be exercised over the Sanskrit studies, and if rewards could be offered for *thorough* proficiency in the studies of the place. At present the certain effects of neglect and the absence of all encouragement are plainly seen in the toles,—they do not teach well what they profess to teach, every thing is chilled by the want of উৎসাহ from those in authority. Now regular examinations (with many rewards) in

* Mansel's *Aldrich*, Pref.

certain text books, held under the superintendence of the Inspector by such a Pandit of the Sanskrit College as Maheça Chandra Nyáyaratna, would give the needed stimulus. Examinations should also be held in the Mugdhabodha or Sanskrit grammar.

2. It seems to me very needful, that, as the *condition* of a liberal help for the Sanskrit studies, Government should insist on some amount of useful learning being also taught. Some arithmetic and perhaps geography and history, and (still better if it were but possible) some little Western Logic and Moral Philosophy would be an invaluable auxiliary and corrective to the peculiar training of a tole. Of course this must all be given in Bengali, and I have no doubt that a sound knowledge of Bengali itself is very rare at Nuddea, even among great Sanskrit scholars. In this way we should break into the narrow circle of prejudice and exclusiveness which hedges round so closely the students of Nuddea, and we should fit them for exercising a beneficial influence on their countrymen. At present they necessarily belong to the past, and are utterly unable to sympathise with or understand the mighty movements round them. A Nuddea student is an exact counterpart to Gibbon's description of the sophist Libanius, "a recluse student, whose mind, regardless of his contemporaries, was incessantly fixed on the Trojan War and the Athenian Commonwealth." Still, after all, their position and training unavoidably give them great influence among their countrymen, especially away from the towns. This influence is, no doubt, at present used everywhere against the progress of education and social improvement; but surely it would be an object well worth striving for, if we could improve, not abolish, the time-honoured tole, and if we could change the character of the students whom its system tends to form, into sound Sanskrit scholars instead of disputatious pedants, and into the friends, instead of the enemies, of native education.

I beg to forward you the above Report, and I must express my deep regret that I have so long delayed sending it. Much of it was written in India before I left, and I had hoped to send it completed soon after my arrival in England, but ill-health and prostration of energy precluded it, and subsequently I found it very difficult to collect the scattered fragments of my notes into a narrative. As it is, I feel it is very imperfect, and had I my Pandit Maheça Chandra by my side, I could easily increase its value tenfold.

As you have expressed a desire to have my Report, such as it is, I have resolutely gone over all my notes and memoranda and rewritten the whole, and I send it with all its shortcomings and defects. It is not easy to write a Report on Nuddea in England. Little details have escaped me which I overlooked at the time, and which I now cannot supply; but I feel sure that the general impression I derived from my visit to the toles is still as vivid as it ever was.

8. From the Secretary to the Government of India in the Home Department, forwarding copies of a report on the manufacture of China grass by Mr. McClintock, American Vice-Consul at Bradford.

Revenue. *India Office, London, 7th March, 1867.*

No. 12.

To His Excellency the Right Honorable the GOVERNOR-GENERAL of India in Council.

SIR,—I transmit to your Excellency in Council thirty copies of a Memorandum, by Mr. McClintock, American Vice-Consul at Bradford, respecting the manufacture of China Grass, and the price which can be obtained for it in this country, which I have received from Her Majesty's Secretary of State for Foreign Affairs.

2. Lord Stanley, in transmitting this paper, informs me that he has ascertained, through the Bradford Chamber of Commerce, that the importance attached by the writer of the Report to this article is not exaggerated, and that nothing but its high price stands in the way of its being largely consumed.

3. Under these circumstances, I agree with the Secretary of State for Foreign Affairs that it will be useful to forward copies of the Report to any of the Officers of your Presidency who reside in places which may be favorable to the cultivation and export of this grass.

I have, &c.,

No. 4159.

CRANBORNE.

Copy of this Despatch, together with three copies of the Report referred to, forwarded to the Secretary, Asiatic Society, Bengal, for information.

By Order,

(Sd.) A. P. HOWELL,

Under Secy. to the Govt. of India.

Fort William, Home Department;

the 22nd April, 1867.